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GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Guide for overcoming common obstacles in implementing RRA

Actionable
version

Definition

Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) seeks to evaluate research, researchers, and institutions in ways that recognise diverse outputs, practices, and impacts. Instead of relying narrowly on journal metrics or prestige, RRA emphasises qualitative judgment, fairness, openness, and alignment with institutional missions.

This guide summarises common barriers faced by universities and research organisations and outlines practical steps to overcome them.

Relevant SCOPE stages

This resource links to the SCOPE Framework in the following ways:

- O – OPTIONS for evaluating: choosing how to assess responsibly and inclusively.
- P – PROBE deeply: testing and refining approaches to ensure fairness, feasibility, and alignment with goals.

When and how to use

Use this resource when:

- Designing or revising career assessment processes (e.g. hiring, promotion, tenure).
- Implementing CoARA or DORA commitments at institutional or departmental level.
- Addressing resistance or confusion about changing assessment practices.

Approach:

1. Map your current practices against SCOPE stages.
2. Identify which obstacles apply (policy, practical, cultural).
3. Select targeted actions (see Guidance) and adapt them to your local context.
4. Engage stakeholders early, especially researchers and leadership.
5. Pilot and iterate, combining qualitative and quantitative evaluation.

Guidance

Common obstacles:

- Policy: misaligned national/international rules, lack of incentives, limited institutional autonomy.
- Practical: cost concerns, limited staff and data, poor coordination.
- Cultural: resistance from researchers or leaders, limited awareness, preference for status quo.

Actions to overcome them:

- Policy collaboration
 - Join international initiatives like CoARA, DORA and Barcelona Declaration.
 - Align institutional policies with broader reform efforts, while allowing flexibility.
 - Advocate nationally for supportive guidelines.
- Investment in infrastructure
 - Develop reliable, open data sources for assessment.
 - Support open infrastructures.
 - Allow the use of structured narrative CVs and qualitative input.
- Culture change strategies
 - Communicate a shared vision.
 - Recognise teamwork, teaching, mentoring, and openness in assessments.
 - Reward peer review and community contributions.
 - Lead by example at senior levels.
- Practical measures
 - Provide staff training on RRA and open science.
 - Engage relevant stakeholders (e.g., researchers) in the process.
 - Simplify new practices (make them easy to use).
 - Pilot innovative schemes (e.g., Recognition & Rewards programmes).

Further reading

- CoARA (2022). Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment. coara.eu/agreement
- DORA (2012). San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment. [sfdora.org](https://www.sfdora.org)
- Hyrkkänen, A.-K. et al. (2023). GraspOS Deliverable D2.1 "OS-aware RRA approaches landscape report". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11098095>
- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>
- Stroobants, K. (2024). Can global reform efforts be diverse and aligned? [LSE Impact Blog](#)